

Cyber Simulation Scenario Generator based on LLM

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**This thesis is submitted to University College Dublin in partial
fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of**

Master of Science in Cybersecurity

School of Computer Science

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August 2025

1 Acknowledgements

I wish to express gratitude to all those who helped me throughout the writing of this thesis.

Firstly, I would like to thank my partner and friends whose patience and support have been valuable throughout this journey. Thank you to my partner and family for providing me with the strength to complete my journey through this MSc.

I would also like to make a special thank you to my project supervisor, Liliana Pasquale, for the unwavering support and understanding during the course of this thesis.

Lastly, I would like to thank my co-workers and leadership of my workplace for their patience and support. Their patience in answering my seemingly endless questions and providing extremely valuable feedback will not be forgotten. It has improved the quality of this research and final solution.

Thank you for your support and contributions.

2 Abstract

This thesis is to address the critical need for realistic and accessible cybersecurity training for executive-level staff who face increasing regulatory pressure to effectively manage cyber crises. The primary objective was to develop an open-source Cyber Simulation Scenario Generator that leverages Large Language Models (LLMs) to create dynamic incident response scenarios.

The methodology involved evaluating various LLMs for their cybersecurity knowledge and implementing a solution based on a purpose-built prompt. This prompt directs the LLM to generate non-technical, decision-tree scenarios specific to organisational contexts. The final implementation also involves a user-friendly Python tool. To ensure the technical validity and relevance of the generated scenarios, the outputs went through a human-in-the-loop validation process, incorporating feedback from cybersecurity professionals and senior executives.

This thesis successfully demonstrates the viability of using LLMs for executive training and incorporates a practical, open-source tool that overcomes the cost and accessibility limitations of commercial solutions. The generator empowers organisations to enhance the decision-making capabilities of their executive staff, improving the overall cyber resilience in the face of constantly evolving cyber threats.

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4 List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full Form
LLM	Large Language Model
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CTF	Capture-the-Flag
IT	Information Technology
NIS2	Network and Information Systems Directive 2
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
SEC	Security and Exchange Commission
MDR	Managed Detection and Response
DDoS	Distributed Denial-of-Service
SOC	Security Operations Centre
NVD	National Vulnerability Database
PII	Personally Identifiable Information
RLHF	Reinforcement Learning with Human Feedback
CoT	Chain-of-Thought
ToT	Tree-of-Thoughts
API	Application Programming Interface
IT	Information Technology
BYOK	Bring-your-own-Key

TTP	Tactics, Techniques and Procedures
GUI	Graphical User Interface

1 Introduction

This thesis is part of a professional project carried out in collaboration with KPMG, which seeks to develop a Large Language Model (LLM)-based Cyber Simulation Generator to create realistic and dynamic cyber scenarios. This thesis aims to establish the groundwork for a comprehensive, engineered solution that will train executive-level personnel in response to both new and existing cyber threats.

In today's world, the emergence of new threats grows in line with the constant increase of intrusions in cyberspace globally. The threats are currently ranging from basic phishing and vishing attacks to cloud and ransomware attacks. In 2024, new and unattributed cloud intrusions increased 26% compared to 2023 [1]. Additionally, there has been a 442% increase in vishing attacks between the first half and the second half of 2024 [1]. This is a highly alarming trend that cannot be ignored.

Although companies implement security awareness training, in many cases, it might not be consistent or up to date. Currently, 62% of companies lack security awareness training [2]. On a more local scale, over 70% of European Union (EU) companies have not taken any steps to train their employees on cybersecurity [3]. This poses an incredibly significant risk as a lack of security training directly correlates to an increase in security breaches. The importance of appropriate cybersecurity training is especially highlighted, given that social engineering and phishing account for 70% to 90% of data breaches [4].

With the constant increase in cybersecurity attacks and breaches, companies need to implement a more effective training structure that will help reduce exposure to social engineering attacks. However, training cannot be isolated to the general workforce to mitigate cyber attacks. Executive-level personnel should also be included in security awareness training, however at executive-level it may look a bit different. At this level, executives must be equipped with enough information to make appropriate decisions at a time of crisis. This includes knowledge of cyber incident response plans, communication protocols, relevant threat vectors and attack surfaces. Studies have shown that organisations with well-trained executive teams respond 40% faster to cyber incidents [5]. Although training may be viewed as an optional component for companies currently, global regulators are seeking more than just basic compliance. Training is being discussed more frequently by regulators, as there is a shift from viewing training as a competitive advantage to recognising its importance for regulatory compliance. Furthermore, in the last few years, more accountability is expected from leadership, specifically in relation to cyber risk governance. Regulatory standards such as NIS2 Directive (EU), SEC Cyber Disclosure Rules (US) and ISO/IEC 27001:2022, all require and mandate executive-level responsibility for cyber risk and impose penalties for non-compliance [5].

This thesis focuses on executive-level training, which bridges a gap in existing solutions which are aimed at training non-technical staff and training

which focuses on capture the flag (CTF) style exercises. Furthermore, this thesis aims to develop a cyber scenario generation tool which employs Large Language Models (LLMs) as a basis for the generation. The purpose of this introduction is to outline the thesis aims, goals, scope, methodology, assumptions and expected outcomes. Additionally, it aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the impact and importance of this thesis.

1.1 Aims of the Thesis

The primary aim of this thesis is to develop a Cyber Simulation Generator. The generator will be used to generate realistic and dynamic cyber scenarios to be used for the training of executive-level and senior-level leadership. Many solutions exist for the training of low-level non-technical staff and of technical staff (such as, IT staff and Cybersecurity staff), but there is a lack of open-source solutions for executive and senior leadership staff. While some solutions are available, many of those are locked behind a paywall, which reduces their accessibility. Additionally, in many cases, scenarios end up being generated manually to ensure that they are appropriate in context to the industry in question.

2 Background

2.1 Introduction

In today's world, cybersecurity is a rapidly growing sector that is constantly changing. It is heavily driven by the continuously increasing number of cyber threats and the continually evolving regulatory requirements. While many companies strive to stay on track with security awareness training and to provide their IT staff with cyber training, executive-level staff tend to be left behind. However, there is a new shift to ensuring that executives are also equipped with enough training and information to deal effectively during times of crisis. With standards such as NIS2 and ISO taking steps to implement requirements for executive-level cyber training, companies are now forced also to train their senior leadership to maintain compliance. NIS2 also goes as far as to enforce penalties on non-compliant companies, which further solidifies the requirement for training. This section explores previous research done on generating security scenarios using LLMs and any existing solutions available.

2.2 Existing Solutions to Cybersecurity Training

Over the years, the form of staff training has evolved from classroom-based presentations to educational videos, cyber ranges, and capture-the-flag (CTF) exercises. These exercises were forced to grow alongside the currently evolving cyber landscape.

2.2.1 Phishing & Security Awareness Training

Currently, in most workplaces, one might encounter a typical security awareness training that revolves around a phishing simulation or another form of social engineering exercise. Those kinds of exercises are extremely effective at teaching staff to recognise key indicators of a phishing or social engineering attempt. The breakdown of those exercises can range from a human created phishing email or Large Language Model created phishing email to presentation-based training. These have been proven in the past to be very effective, where participant awareness increased from 77.75% to 93.24% after the training [6].

2.2.2 Traditional Methods

Another traditional form of cyber training includes classroom-based training. This type of training tends to be the most structured, cost-effective and scalable. It allows a larger number of people to be addressed within a single, instructor-led sitting. Traditional training like this is highly relatable to most people however, it is a type of passive learning and usually results in poor engagement. It can also result in poor skill retention compared to similar-style online training, where users can undergo the training without supervision. A significant disadvantage of traditional training is the time constraints it imposes. It tends to be possible in most workplaces to facilitate classroom-based training for new

onboardings however, for existing employees it may be difficult to spare the time cost for classroom-based training.

2.2.3 E-Learning & Online Training

As mentioned earlier, a more modern approach to traditional classroom-based training is online training or E-learning platforms. These allow staff to be trained remotely, without the need for in-person training and supervision. This type of training poses the same advantages as traditional training, however this has the added benefit of having better scalability and flexibility. Many workplaces choose this form of training as it gives them the ability to set a deadline for the training, rather than needing to ensure that all relevant staff are available at the same time. This does not come without any disadvantages. E-Learning and online platform training tend to have very limited hands-on experience and can have variable engagement depending on how the course is structured. The structure of many of those courses tends to be an educational video or presentation where the in-person instructor led experience has just been moved to an online experience.

2.2.4 Gamification of Training

This is where the more modern type of training becomes much more engaging and hands-on. The evolution of training from traditional speaker-listener situations to hands-on gamified and scenario-based training is increasingly more important. While traditional training tends to be repetitive with very little differences from before, more modern scenario-based training has the advantage of being tailored specifically to the industry and audience needs. With the industries of the world being varied and with different regulatory requirements, physical and cyber threats, and skill requirements, it is important to tailor the training to exactly that. While in the cyber sector, the majority of threats can fit into one of the few categories, it is important to consider that the way they present themselves may be different. Furthermore, traditional style learning is an extremely effective way to raise cybersecurity awareness amongst non-technical staff. Non-technical staff is usually most susceptible to social engineering attempts such as, phishing, vishing and bribery for insider threat attacks. On the other hand, technical staff may be more aware of those types of attacks and may be more likely to be exposed to other techniques such as network reconnaissance, vulnerability scanning and password spray attacks. Ensuring that technical staff are adequately trained and prepared for this is incredibly important. More specific technical training is important, which is why simulation and scenario-based tabletop exercise training has emerged.

Gamification of training opened the world of training to more possibilities. It allows users to be more engaged with what is presented before them and encourages hands-on experience. In a workplace scenario, most staff may never directly see or experience many positive threat events; therefore, it is important to allow them to experience it first-hand in a safe environment. Experiencing threat event scenarios allows staff to be able to identify similar situations that may occur in their workplace, and with appropriate training also allows them to mitigate it effectively too.

The use of gamified training is further reinforced by a study carried out by Tommy van Steen and Julia R.A. Deeleman in 2021 called “Successful Gamification of Cybersecurity Training”. The purpose of that research was to present a rigorous experimental evaluation of a cybersecurity serious game applicable for cybersecurity training [7]. The study employed a Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) as the theoretical foundation, which the behaviour results fit into four key factors: Attitudes, Social Norms, Perceived Behavioural Control and Behavioural Intentions. Using three separate controlled games, the authors were able to test a group of participants. The games ranged from no cybersecurity content to some content, to a fully cybersecurity-focused game. Furthermore, the results of this research show that a theory-informed serious game on cybersecurity can have a positive effect on self-reported TPB scores and behaviour [7]. However, it does specify that teaching about best practices through a game does not lead to significant changes, but rather an interactive game, encouraging the use of cybersecurity practices would result in significant changes.

2.3 LLMs in Cybersecurity

Ever since the emergence of Generative AI, the usage of LLMs in cybersecurity has attracted a significant amount of attention in both academia and industry. LLMs such as GPT-4, LLaMa and Claude represent a shift in the way understanding natural language and reasoning can be applied to security tasks. Tasks such as intrusion detection, malware analysis, phishing detection and automated incident response. While traditional machine learning models have long supported anomaly detection and malware classification, LLMs offer unprecedented capabilities in contextual reasoning, adaptability, and the generation of structured outputs from unstructured sources [8].

2.3.1 Acceleration of Incident Response

The speed at which security teams can investigate incidents is extremely critical to reducing any potential damage to the company. Currently, conventional cybersecurity methods rely on the use of signature-based detections and rules. Those, however, can be unreliable in detecting novel or more sophisticated attack vectors.

This is where LLMs can provide two major benefits: dynamic playbook generation and automated incident response. Compared to traditional Managed Detection and Response (MDR) solutions, LLMs are trained on massive datasets and excel at learning complex patterns. LLMs can rapidly ingest internal system logs, intrusion detection alerts, and endpoint telemetry, condensing thousands of entries into coherent narratives highlighting root causes, attack chains, and impacted assets [9]. This allows analysts to skip over manual triage steps and instead focus on decision-making. The large datasets that LLMs are trained on, in conjunction with internal data logging, allow for the detection of more complex patterns and anomalies that general, human-created detection rules may not detect. A study by Hassanin et al. (2023) presents a comprehensive survey of various LLM applications in cyber

defence, highlighting their superior capability in detecting various and novel threats such as zero-day vulnerabilities, distributed denial-of-service (DDoS) attacks and phishing attempts. These LLMs use their contextual comprehension to analyse both code-level and behavioural indicators, thereby enhancing early warning systems and reducing false positives [10]. Furthermore, every Security Operations Centre (SOC) is plagued by what is called alert fatigue. Alert fatigue happens when analysts must go through a large number of false positive alerts, usually leading to slower response times, increased stress, and, in more extreme cases, missed critical threats. LLMs can mitigate this issue by performing contextual alert triage. Instead of presenting raw alerts, an LLM can cluster related events, annotate them with natural-language explanations, and suggest confidence-weighted mitigation steps [11].

Beyond operational benefits, LLMs are also a powerful tool for research and analysis. One of the key strengths of LLMs is their adaptive learning. Unlike a typical MDR system, which uses static rules, LLM's knowledge set is continuously updated from threat intelligence feeds, real-time attack data, and historical incident response. This dynamic learning ability is key to maintaining efficiency of security operations throughout the rapidly evolving threat landscape. For instance, researchers have demonstrated that LLMs can synthesise patterns from the MITRE ATT&CK framework and National Vulnerability Database (NVD) to highlight frequently exploited vectors [12]. Such insights can provide support for policymakers and industry leaders in guiding regulatory frameworks and prioritising defensive measures.

2.4 LLM Risks and Issues

While LLMs are extremely powerful tools that can be utilised to enhance cybersecurity operations, their integration is not without significant disadvantages, risks, and ethical concerns. These issues can range from various technical shortcomings, such as hallucination and adversarial susceptibility, to operational concerns, such as data privacy, bias, and possible misuse by adversaries. Furthermore, the large-scale deployment of LLMs in cybersecurity contexts raises critical governance, trust, and explainability challenges [13]. Understanding these challenges is crucial to responsibly using LLMs in the sensitive domain of cybersecurity.

2.4.1 Hallucination

One of the most widely known limitations of LLMs is their inclination to a phenomenon called “hallucination”. This phenomenon is when a model generates plausible but factually incorrect or fabricated information or misleading outputs. In cybersecurity, this poses significant risks as false threat intelligence, erroneous vulnerability reports, or incorrect remediation guidance could result in overlooked attacks, misguided security policies, and misinformed decisions. In some cases, studies show that AI hallucination rates can reach as high as 45% in some scenarios [14], raising concerns about reliance on AI-generated outputs without additional human verification. Additionally, studies show that GPT-based models frequently misclassify benign software

behaviours as malicious or fabricate non-existent CVEs when prompted with vulnerability-related queries [15]. This specific unreliability can undermine the direct use of LLMs in security-critical workflows such as intrusion detection and vulnerability management, where accuracy is required. Huang et al. [16] provide a taxonomy of hallucination types in LLMs, emphasising that hallucination is often inevitable due to training on incomplete or noisy datasets. Xu et al. [17] further argue that hallucination is often an intrinsic limitation of transformer-based models, highlighting the inherent unreliability of LLM outputs in high-stakes decision-making.

2.4.2 Data Privacy and Security Risks

The integration of LLMs within a cybersecurity workflow often requires providing access to sensitive organisational information, including but not limited to, network logs, device logs, incident reports, architectures, and personally identifiable information (PII). Without appropriate safeguards, sensitive data could be inadvertently leaked or used as training datasets for future model outputs, which violates regulatory requirements such as GDPR [18], [19].

2.4.3 Vulnerability to Adversarial Misuse

As discussed in section 2.4.2, LLMs integrated in cybersecurity environments are usually granted access to sensitive information. A major risk that companies currently deal with is the potential leakage of PII and other sensitive information through LLMs. One of the ways that this is possible is through a method called Prompt Injection.

Prompt injection attacks can take two main forms: direct and indirect injections. Direct injection involves the embedding of malicious instructions within user inputs to manipulate the outputs from an LLM. Indirect prompt injection, although similar in result, is where malicious instructions are concealed within seemingly benign content that the LLM will process, such as web pages or documents. These kinds of attacks can lead to unauthorised information disclosure, execution of malicious code, or generation of potentially harmful content. A study carried out by Benjamin et al. [20] systemically analysed the vulnerability of 36 LLMs to prompt injection, revealing that 56% of the tests led to successful manipulations, with larger models being more susceptible. Furthermore, Google has reported such tactics targeting its LLM, Gemini, leading to unauthorised access and data breaches [21].

The susceptibility of LLMs to adversarial techniques, such as prompt injection, has major implications for cybersecurity. Threat Actors can exploit such weaknesses to manipulate and potentially disable threat detection systems, exfiltrate data, or spread misinformation.

2.5 Existing Cyber Scenario Generators

The initial wave of artificial intelligence (AI) integration in cybersecurity training has mainly focused on enhancing the realism and scalability of exercises for SOC analysts, incident responders, and the general workforce.

2.5.1 AI-Enhanced Cyber Ranges and Technical Drills

Cyber ranges are purpose-built virtual environments that allow for technical staff to practise defending against and responding to attacks in a safe, controlled setting. These environments tend to be complex to build and require manual input in developing the cyber scenarios within them.

Immersive Labs stands out with its "AI Scenario Generator", which allows training administrators to use simple text prompts to create custom cyber exercises and crisis simulations. This capability significantly reduces the development overhead, enabling organisations to train against unseen before threats, like a new ransomware variant, almost as soon as they are identified.

RangeForce complements its interactive cyber range modules with an "AI Tutor" that provides guidance to professionals during exercises, personalising the learning experience. Similarly, the security validation platform Cymulate employs an "AI Copilot" to translate raw threat intelligence data into actionable security assessments and an "AI Template Creator" to generate attack scenarios from threat advisories.

For government and military applications, Circadence has developed "RangeGPT". RangeGPT is an AI-driven tool that uses natural language to develop mission-specific cyber range exercises, showcasing the demand for rapid customisation in high-risk environments. Cloud Range has also integrated AI-aware threats into its live-fire simulations, exposing trainees to more advanced challenges like polymorphic malware and AI-generated deepfake phishing attacks.

2.5.2 AI-Generated Phishing and Social Engineering Simulations

Given that an overwhelming percentage of breaches are due to human error, AI is being leveraged to create more convincing and adaptive social engineering simulations. These platforms move beyond generic templates to craft phishing emails and messages that are highly personalised and reflect more modern techniques used by malicious actors.

OutThink utilises an AI-powered system to design realistic phishing scenarios that adapt to an organisation's specific context. Jericho Security offers a similar platform that can build and launch custom phishing simulations in minutes based on the latest available real-world threats. Pushing the boundaries further, Adaptive leverages OpenAI's generative technology to create deepfake voice, SMS (smishing), and email phishing simulations. This aids in preparing employees for the next generation of social engineering attacks. Phishup also uses AI to generate editable phishing templates directly from text prompts, allowing for deep customisation of training campaigns.

2.5.3 AI-Powered Crisis Simulators and Tabletop Exercises

Traditional tabletop exercises are often static and predictable. The implementation of AI introduces an overseer element to a traditional tabletop exercise, capable of altering the scenario in real-time based on the leadership team's decisions. This, in turn, creates a more realistic and challenging environment.

The SANS Institute, a leader in cybersecurity certification and training, has integrated a custom-configured LLM tool into its LDR553: Cyber Incident Management course. This tool is specifically designed to help leaders generate non-technical, accessible tabletop exercises that test executive awareness and incident response processes. It automates the creation of exercise structures, facilitator guides, and participant materials, reducing the barrier to creating repeatable leadership exercises.

The previously mentioned Immersive Labs platform is also directly applicable to C-suite training. Its AI Scenario Generator can be prompted to create high-level crisis simulations focused on business impact, such as "a ransomware attack on our supply chain partner during a major product launch," allowing executives to focus on strategic dilemmas rather than technical issues.

3 Methodology

3.1 Introduction to Section

This chapter discusses the methodology for selecting the appropriate large language model. The selection is an important component of this thesis as the quality, adaptability and appropriate dataset training of the model are crucial for accurate generation of cyber simulations. This thesis aims to address specific needs that were initially outlined by KPMG through an investigation into various types of LLM models.

3.2 Choosing of LLMs

A number of evaluation criteria were defined under which each LLM will be tested. The following criteria were considered:

3.2.1 Model capability and Adaptability

The chosen model must demonstrate advanced comprehension of cybersecurity terminology, attack vectors and system architectures. Furthermore, it must support scenario narratives that reflect realistic adversarial tactics, techniques, and procedures that are consistent with frameworks such as MITRE ATT&CK and CAPEC.

3.2.2 Scenario Diversity

The model must have the capacity to generate a wide variety of attack and defence scenarios. Diversity of scenarios is important to allow for the generation of multiple simulations for the same input variables.

3.2.3 Training Data and Alignment

While the training datasets of most LLMs are not publicly known, preference was given to models that have broad exposure to technical domains, specifically in relation to cybersecurity and IT.

3.2.4 Prompt Engineering Flexibility

One of the requirements as part of this thesis is the ability to create a repeatable process which will provide consistent outputs. As part of this requirement, the chosen LLM cannot deviate from the initial structure between outputs. Therefore, the model must support prompt engineering techniques to ensure consistency and control over the generated outputs. Availability of fine-tuning or reinforcement learning with human feedback (RLHF) was considered an advantage.

3.2.5 Security and Ethical Considerations

During the selection process, security and ethical safeguards were considered. Ensuring that each model evaluated had appropriate safeguards to minimise

misuse, such as generating malicious code. Additionally, open-source models were examined for security risks relating to model poisoning or unauthorised fine-tuning.

3.2.6 Licensing and Accessibility

One of the main considerations of this project is the open-source usage of this. The practical feasibility of using a model in academic research was evaluated with respect to API access, cost and licensing terms. Preference was given to freely available models and models with academic research licensing.

3.3 Model Evaluation and Findings

The models that were evaluated were: ChatGPT, Grok, Claude, Perplexity, Gemini, Qwen2 and DeepSeek. There was more emphasis put on testing publicly available models however, two additional models were evaluated on a local testing machine using LM Studio.

3.3.1 Model Capability and Adaptability

To evaluate this requirement, each model was asked a range of questions related to cybersecurity. Each question required the models to present a written report on a technique and map it to the MITRE ATT&CK framework. Examples of questions asked include, “Can you create a write-up on spear-fishing chains with reference to MITRE ATT&CK framework?” and “Using the MITRE ATT&CK framework and previous real-time events, present a scenario where ransomware has been deployed and the initial attack vector was an insider threat.”

3.3.1.1 ChatGPT (OpenAI, GPT-4.5 backend)

At the time of testing, ChatGPT was built on the GPT-4.5 backend (Note: During writing, this has changed to GPT-5 with no free ability to choose another model). It demonstrated a good understanding of advanced language. It showed great competence in technical content, responsiveness to context and structured output. With appropriate prompting, MITRE-type attack narratives were generated with good structure, including additional content such as variants of the scenarios and defensive considerations. Hallucinations were exhibited when asked to reference the outputs, especially with more technical prompts. Hallucinations were mitigated in most cases when asked to reference material to actual web sources. As an additional mention, ChatGPT was the fastest to produce a response of all models.

3.3.1.2 Grok (xAI)

The Grok model emphasises conversational ability rather than deep technical reasoning. While the model provided good general scenario generation, it lacked considerable technical depth compared to the other models. It provided examples of real-life events as part of its outputs; however, the structure was very conversational and informal. There was a lack of consistency in the outputs, making them hard to follow. An honourable mention, though, is that

Grok provided hyperlinks to each technique mentioned, as well as hyperlinks to the real threat events it mentioned in the outputs.

3.3.1.3 Claude (Sonnet 4)

Claude models are trained through a method called Constitutional AI (CAI). CAI is a method developed by Anthropic for training AI models to align with a specific set of rules or principles, otherwise known as a “constitution”. The goal of this method is to make AI systems helpful, harmless and more controllable without requiring extensive human feedback [22]. The outputs from Claude were coherent, technical and presented a strong understanding of structured attack procedures. It provided a strong understanding of the ATT&CK framework with good breakdowns of the information and references. Unfortunately, it was one of the slower models to produce an output.

3.3.1.4 Perplexity

Perplexity is a model that integrates live, web-retrieved content, which allows for factual grounding. Additionally, similarly to Claude, it also employs Constitutional AI methods. However, for prompts requiring adversarial strategies, it lacked technical understanding and defaulted to generic narratives available within web articles. Some relation to the ATT&CK framework was made however, it was very vague and lacked understanding of the content. Additionally, references to past threat events were vague and not directly related to the prompt. Furthermore, the model was extremely slow to generate outputs compared to the other models.

3.3.1.5 Gemini 2.5 Pro (Google AI Studio)

Gemini presented robust reasoning. When asked the test questions, the candidate presented a good understanding of advanced language and technical content. Although structured differently, the content of the outputs of Gemini was very similar to ChatGPT. However, the content of the outputs was more descriptive, and scenario based in comparison to ChatGPT where the content was more technical and less situational. For example, Gemini gave real-world examples of previous attacks with references to online articles. Gemini has multi-modal potential which may provide useful for diagrams however, that was outside the scope of the thesis. Additionally, this was one of the fastest models to produce an output.

3.3.1.6 Qwen2

Compared to the other models, Qwen2 is an open-source model that was trained with technical data, which showed promise in the cybersecurity domain. Moreover, testing of this model was carried out on a local machine rather than through a web-based interface like the other models. This was done to test the feasibility of a local deployment of the model. During the testing, technical alignment and native knowledge of cybersecurity frameworks was limited however, with additional dataset training it could be improved. Additionally, hallucination control heavily depended on prompt engineering. One consideration to be made is that a locally deployed model will not contain up-to-date knowledge, which does put it at a disadvantage.

3.3.1.7 DeepSeek

Similar to Qwen2, DeepSeek is an open-source model. This model was also locally deployed. The native knowledge of cybersecurity frameworks was extremely poor, with the outputs being quite vague. Similarly to Qwen2, consideration must be made that a locally deployed model will not contain up-to-date knowledge and will require the curation of an appropriate training dataset.

3.3.2 Scenario Diversity

To test scenario diversity, each model was asked to create various scenarios ranging from phishing attacks, insider threats, supply-chain compromises, cloud misconfigurations, and zero-day exploit contexts. Prompts were kept to minimal information to check the behaviour of the models, and each prompt was re-run 5 times. Testing was carried out to check how much variability each model can create without repeating itself.

3.3.2.1 ChatGPT (OpenAI, GPT-4.5 backend)

ChatGPT created well-structured, consistent outputs. It varied the parameters in relation to the potential company the scenario related to. The attack steps initially varied; however, after the third input, the model began repeating itself. Specifically, outputs 3-5 had extremely similar initial access steps. The persistence and privilege techniques were repeated; however, the potential real-time scenario was varied across all. The end stages of all the attacks were repeated in most outputs with very little difference between the scenarios. The model related all the steps involved in the ATT&CK framework and provided good post-attack lessons and recommendations.

3.3.2.2 Grok (xAI)

Grok produced clear scenarios with a timeline aspect. The stage-by-stage scenario was directly related to the ATT&CK framework; however, there was very little variance between the scenarios. Each scenario generated by the model had repetitive aspects, with very little diversity. There is potential for diversifying the output through some prompt engineering. A question does arise, however: if the inputs are similar enough, will the generated scenario be potentially the same or with very little difference?

3.3.2.3 Claude (Sonnet 4)

Unlike ChatGPT and Grok, Claude would not produce a new scenario if asked the same prompt. The only way to have Claude generate a new output was to start with a new chat again. Furthermore, the first produced output was very detailed with day-by-day breakdowns, in-depth analysis and good specifics. Although, unlike the other models, Claude did not relate the scenario to the ATT&CK framework making it a less technical output. Subsequent outputs produced much more vague and increasingly basic scenarios. There may be potential for diversifying the outputs with appropriate prompt engineering.

3.3.2.4 Perplexity

Compared to the other models, Perplexity was able to produce a very in-depth and realistic attack scenario. The generated scenario had very good technical details and was extremely realistic, as it was based on past threat events. Additionally, the model provided a great deal of depth at every step, and the scenarios varied significantly between each generation. This model generated the longest outputs, which in turn meant that it took the longest to produce an output.

3.3.2.5 Gemini 2.5 Pro (Google AI Studio)

Gemini provided very in-depth, technical outputs which were realistic. It showed extra creativity by adding in details for URLs, passwords, and filenames. The scenarios were well structured, and the threat events varied between scenarios. Each scenario was adequately long, and the generation time was quite short, approximately 30 seconds. Direct relationship to ATT&CK framework were omitted however, each scenario had a realistic progression.

3.3.2.6 Qwen2

Due to the low knowledge of cybersecurity, the outputs were very vague and often limited. With appropriate prompt engineering and training the model may show some potential however due to time and resource constraints, localised testing is outside the scope of this thesis.

3.3.2.7 DeepSeek

Similarly to Qwen2, due to the low knowledge of cybersecurity, the outputs were very vague and often limited. With appropriate prompt engineering and training the model may show some potential however due to time and resource constraints, localised testing is outside the scope of this thesis.

3.3.3 Training Data and Alignment

The ability of the LLMs to produce effective cybersecurity scenarios depends significantly on the quality and diversity of their training datasets. This section explores the training methodologies of the models and their alignment with the cybersecurity space. Additionally, this will assess their suitability for generating realistic cyber simulations.

3.3.3.1 ChatGPT (OpenAI, GPT-4.5 backend)

ChatGPT uses publicly available online content that is freely accessible. Data from behind paywalls and the dark web is not gathered [23]. The model uses Reinforcement Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF), which aligns the model more with human values and preferences. This process involves human reviewers providing feedback on the model outputs, which constantly adjusts the model's behaviour to enhance its ability to generate contextually appropriate and ethically sound responses. OpenAI also openly admits that the model does exhibit some bias and can produce inaccuracies [24].

3.3.3.2 Grok (xAI)

Similar to ChatGPT, Grok was initially trained on publicly available data up to a certain point in time. Since Grok is related to the X (Twitter) platform, this model has been proven to be trained on user-generated content such as public posts, user interactions, inputs and results from users. Furthermore, there have been incidents where the model generated harmful and offensive content due to the training data.

3.3.3.3 Claude (Sonnet 4)

As mentioned previously, Claude employs the use of Constitution AI, which represents a step forward in AI alignment. Claude Sonnet 4 was trained on large, diverse datasets. The training data was a mix of publicly available information up to March 2025, as well as some non-public data such as data-labelling services, users who opted in to share their data, paid contractors, and internal Anthropic data [25].

3.3.3.4 Perplexity

Unlike the other models, perplexity utilises a knowledge retrieval algorithm that allows it to access current information from a vast array of sources. It employs Constitutional AI and RLHF in its training. The initial pre-training knowledge cutoff is around October 2023, but that is an approximate date that is available.

3.3.3.5 Gemini 2.5 Pro (Google AI Studio)

Unfortunately, Google is not very transparent about what training data was used with Gemini. From documentation alone it is difficult to assess its suitability for generating cybersecurity scenarios. Additionally, as the details about training data is not publicly available, it does raise concerns about potential bias in the training data.

Gemini 2.5 Pro did provide a direct answer around what dataset was used, “My training data consists of a massive and diverse collection of text and code, drawn from the public internet and Google's internal datasets” [26].

3.3.3.6 Qwen2

Since this is an open-source model, there is a lot of transparency around the training data used. Qwen2 has been trained on specialised datasets, including Qwen2.5-Math and Qwen2.5-Coder.

3.3.3.7 DeepSeek

DeepSeek, similarly to Qwen2, is an open-source model. The basic training of DeepSeek-R1 consisted of using Reinforcement Learning (RL) however, a huge disadvantage of this method is challenges such as poor readability. This can be solved using multi-stage training.

The main training data that was used to train DeepSeek is web-hosted data, code datasets, dialogue data and mathematical and scientific texts. This does give DeepSeek quite a vast set of training data. Although the dataset is

very large, there is a potential for bias and errors, as a large subset of the data is based on public forums and public code repositories such as GitHub.

3.4 Prompt Generation

As discussed in the previous sections, LLMs are powerful tools for natural language understanding and generation. All the mentioned models demonstrate impressive abilities to generate coherent text, answer questions and can even simulate reasoning processes. However, the raw power alone of these models can sometimes prove to be latent and often requires careful guidance to be used effectively. Central to their effectiveness is the prompt, which acts as the instruction or input that the LLM utilises as guidance towards producing a relevant and high-quality output. Prompts can be described further as a set of instructions or context which the model can use to direct its output. The science of creating effective prompts is known as prompt engineering. This has become a crucial area of research and practice.

3.4.1 Defining Prompt Generation

A prompt itself is simply defined as the input provided to an LLM. A prompt can be a single word, a question, a phrase or a paragraph's worth of instructions. For example:

- A minimal prompt: "What is the capital of Italy?"
- A structured prompt: "You are a professional travel agent. Create a detailed, three-day itinerary for Liverpool. Include local cultural attractions, restaurants, entertainment centres and transport tips."

3.4.2 Why Prompt Generation Matters

Unlike traditional software and algorithms, where rules are explicitly embedded in the software, LLMs operate on probabilistic language prediction. The same model can provide drastically different outputs depending on the context of the prompt, phrasing and its structure. Through the use of effective prompt generation, it is possible to direct the model toward accuracy of output, relevance and tone.

3.4.3 Fundamental Prompting Techniques

The initial interactions with LLMs are often guided by fundamental prompting strategies that are straightforward but very useful in directing the LLMs. The following techniques represent the primary methods for communicating tasks to an LLM and the basis upon which more complex prompts can be created.

3.4.3.1 Instruction-based Prompting

Instruction-based prompting broadly refers to framing an input as a set of direct instructions. It is arguably the most direct form of interaction with an LLM. It involves providing the model with a clear and concise direction of the task it is

expected to perform [27]. This method of prompt engineering leverages the extensive training of a model on natural language to understand and execute the commands. The core principle of instruction-based prompting is the explicit statement of intent, which minimises ambiguity and guides the model toward the desired output [28].

The actual effectiveness of prompting depends on the clarity and specificity of the instructions provided. Poorly worded or vague prompts can lead to the generation of irrelevant or nonsensical responses. Conversely, well-crafted instructions can enable LLMs to perform a wide variety of tasks with a high degree of accuracy [27]. For example, instead of using a generic prompt such as “talk about climate change”, a more detailed instruction-based prompt would look like, “Summarise the key findings of the latest IPCC report on climate change in 500 words”. Research has shown that the structure and phrasing of instructions can significantly impact model performance, with more detailed and explicit instructions generally yielding better results [29]. The composition of a prompt, including the input, context, instructions, and desired output format, are crucial components that work together to guide the model’s output [28], [30].

3.4.3.2 Zero-shot prompting

Zero-shot prompting style is the practice of presenting an LLM with a task it has not been explicitly trained to perform, without providing any examples on how to complete it [31]. This technique relies explicitly on the ability of the model to generalise based on the amount of information it has learned during its pre-training phase. An example of this is a user asking a model to translate a sentence from English to Polish, even if the model has not been fine-tuned on a dataset specifically for translation. This style of prompting forces the model to leverage its understanding of both languages and the patterns that it observed within its training data to generate the translation.

The seminal work on LLMs demonstrated their inherent zero-shot capabilities, which emerge as the models are scaled to a sufficient size [32]. The ability of LLMs to perform zero-shot reasoning can be evoked through the use of prompting phrases such as “Let’s solve this step by step” [33]. The performance of zero-shot reasoning can vary extensively as it is often dependent on the complexity of the task and the specific model being used. While it can sometimes be quite effective for simpler tasks, its performance often falls short on more complex reasoning problems [34].

3.4.3.3 Few-Shot Prompting

Due to limitations of zero-shot prompting, particularly in more complex tasks, few-shot prompting was developed. The premise of this technique involves providing the LLM with a small number of examples, or “shots”, of the desired input-output format within the prompt itself [35]. Those examples serve as in-context learning or conditioning of the model to understand the task better and generate a response that aligns with the provided examples [34].

For example, to perform sentiment analysis, a few-shot prompt might include a few sentences labelled with their corresponding sentiment (e.g., "Sentence: 'I love this movie!' Sentiment: Positive," "Sentence: 'The plot was

very confusing.' Sentiment: Negative"). The model then uses these examples to classify a new, unlabelled sentence. Research has shown that even a small number of examples can significantly improve performance on a wide range of tasks [35], [36]. The effectiveness of few-shot prompting is influenced by factors such as the choice and order of the examples provided [36].

Few-shot prompting can be highly effective; however, it does feature some limitations. For more complex reasoning tasks, even with some examples, the model may still struggle to generate the correct output.

3.4.4 Enhanced Prompting Techniques

While the fundamental prompting techniques are sufficient for most tasks, more complex problems that demand more complex reasoning necessitate a more sophisticated approach to prompting. This section will explore various advanced prompting techniques designed to enable more robust and transparent reasoning from LLMs.

3.4.4.1 Role-Based Prompting

Role-based prompting, also referred to as person prompting, involves assigning a specific role or person to the LLM to direct its responses. This technique leverages the model's ability to simulate different styles of speaking, tones, and areas of expertise based on the persona it is asked to adopt [37]. By instructing the model to "act as" an expert in a particular field, a figure from history or even an inanimate object, users can force the model to produce more nuanced, contextually appropriate, and repeatedly more accurate responses.

As an example, here is a prompt that begins with "You are an experienced red team analyst. Explain the intricacies of an adversary-in-the-middle attack and the impact it will have on a financial company". This type of prompt is likely to ensure the model generates a more detailed and professional response than a simpler query about the same topic. Research has shown that role-playing can greatly enhance the reasoning abilities of LLMs in a zero-shot setting [38]. A strategically designed role-play prompting methodology has been shown to consistently surpass the standard zero-shot approach across various reasoning benchmarks [38]. This technique can be particularly useful for tasks that require a very specific perspective or style of communication, such as generating creative content, providing educational explanations or engaging in empathetic conversations [39]. The effectiveness of role-based prompting lies in its ability to narrow the vast space of possible responses to those that are consistent with the assigned persona, thereby increasing the relevance and quality of the output [40].

3.4.4.2 Chain-of-Thought Prompting

Chain-of-Thought prompting has emerged as a transformative technique for improving the reasoning capabilities of LLMs. This is particularly true on tasks that require multiple steps to solve, such as arithmetic, commonsense, and symbolic reasoning problems [41]. CoT prompting encourages the LLM to break down a complex problem into a series of intermediate reasoning steps before arriving at a final answer [41]. This process mirrors human cognitive

processes and has been shown to significantly improve the performance on a variety of reasoning tasks [42]. The key insight behind CoT is that the model is better able to follow a logical path and avoid errors that might occur if it were to attempt to solve the problem in a single step. For instance, when solving a math word problem, the prompt would not only provide the final answer but also the intermediate calculations and logical steps taken to reach it [41].

Further research has explored the nuances of what makes CoT an effective prompting technique. Interestingly, studies have found that CoT reasoning is possible even with invalid demonstrations. Prompting with incorrect reasoning steps can still achieve a significant portion of the performance obtained with a valid CoT, as long as the format of the reasoning is present [43]. This suggests that the structure of the reasoning process is an important step that guides the model. The evolution of CoT techniques reflects the rapid progress in the field, with various implementations ranging from simple zero-shot approaches to more sophisticated methods [42].

3.4.4.3 Self-Consistency Prompting

Building upon the foundation of CoT prompting, Self-Consistency prompting is a technique that enhances the reasoning performance of LLMs using a decoding strategy. Proposed by Wang et al. (2022), self-consistency replaces the naïve greedy decoding used in standard CoT with a more robust sampling method [44]. Instead of generating a single reasoning path, the self-consistency approach samples multiple, diverse reasoning paths from the language model's decoder. The final answer is then determined by marginalising out these reasoning paths and selecting the most consistent answer among the various outputs [44].

The thought behind self-consistency is that a complex reasoning problem often has many valid paths to the correct solution. By exploring a variety of reasoning processes, the model is more likely to converge on the correct answer, even if some of the possible paths contain errors. Research has proven that this method can significantly boost the performance of CoT prompting on a range of arithmetic and commonsense reasoning benchmarks, with notable improvements on datasets like GSM8K, SVAMP, and AQUA [44]. The process involves three main steps: first, prompting the LLM with a CoT prompt; second, generating a diverse set of reasoning paths by sampling from the model's decoder; and third, aggregating the answers and selecting the one that appears most frequently [44].

3.4.4.4 Tree-of-Thoughts Prompting

While Chain-of-Thought and Self-Consistency improve reasoning by generating linear sequences of thought, the Tree-of-Thoughts (ToT) employs a different approach. ToT introduces a more sophisticated approach that enables LLMs to explore different reasoning paths in a more deliberate and strategic manner [45]. ToT generalises the CoT approach by organising the reasoning process into a tree structure where each node represents a “thought”. This “thought” is a coherent unit of text that serves as an intermediate step toward solving a problem [45].

The ToT framework allows the LLM to perform more deliberate decision-making by considering multiple different reasoning paths at the same time. The model can self-evaluate the progress made by each thought and decide which path to explore further. As part of this framework, it can also look ahead or go back, when necessary, which allows for a more global and strategic approach to problem-solving [45]. This goes against the typical process of standard LLMs, which typically follow a token-level, left-to-right decision-making process.

The ToT framework has been shown to significantly enhance the problem-solving abilities of language models on tasks that require non-trivial planning or search, such as the Game of 24, creative writing, and mini crosswords [45]. In the Game of 24, for example, where GPT-4 with CoT prompting solved only 4% of tasks, the ToT method achieved a success rate of 74% [45]. This is achieved by combining the language model's ability to generate and evaluate thoughts with search algorithms like breadth-first search or depth-first search, which systematically explore the tree of thoughts [46].

3.4.4.5 System Prompting

Unlike the previously mentioned prompting techniques, which are used to guide LLMs responses for individual tasks, there is an additional overarching layer of instruction that can influence the entire interaction with an LLM: the system prompt. A system prompt is a high-level instruction that sets the context, constraints, and persona for the LLM's behaviour throughout a conversation. It is essentially a guiding framework that will influence all of the models' subsequent responses.

While most user prompts are typically focused on a specific task, the system prompt provides a more general set of instructions that the model should adhere to. To give an example, a system prompt might instruct the model to always respond in a formal tone, never to provide medical advice, or to adopt the persona of a helpful and friendly assistant. This style of initial instruction ensures that the model's output will remain consistent and gives additional control over the model.

Research in this area has mainly focused on optimising these system-level instructions to maximise the general performance of LLMs. A study by Zhang et al. (2024) proposed an edit-based genetic algorithm to iteratively construct system prompts that improve a model's performance across a wide range of tasks [47]. Their findings indicate that a single, optimised system prompt can perform on par with task-specific prompts and that combining system-level and task-level optimisations can lead to further improvements [47]. This also highlights the complementary nature of two different levels of prompting. Furthermore, well-optimised system prompts have been shown to generalise effectively across different model families, parameter sizes, and even languages [47].

3.4.5 Modular and Constrained Prompting Techniques

As the complexity of a task assigned to an LLM increases, so does the need for more refined control methods and task decomposition. Negative prompting and prompt chaining are two types of techniques that allow greater precision in

guiding LLM outputs. The former provides explicit constraints to avoid undesirable content, while the latter breaks down intricate workflows into manageable, sequential steps.

3.4.5.1 Negative Prompting

Negative prompting is a technique that instructs a language model on what to avoid in its response, rather than solely what to include [48]. This method of exclusion is used to refine outputs, prevent the generation of biased or harmful content, and improve overall relevance and accuracy [48]. For example, a user with the goal of generating an image of a natural landscape might add a negative prompt like “no cars, no buildings”. In text generation, it could be used to prevent the model from featuring certain entities or adopting a certain tone [48].

The advantage of using negative prompting lies in its ability to offer a direct form of content filtering at the point of generation. Research has explored the use of negative prompts to align LLMs with human values and preferences by explicitly penalising the model for producing harmful or biased responses [49]. The use of this dual feedback mechanism, which encourages desirable behaviours while simultaneously steering the model away from undesirable ones, can be crucial in contexts where avoiding harm is important [49]. The psychological foundations of this technique suggest that, in specific contexts, negative prompts can force a model to consider alternative pathways, potentially leading to more creative and relevant outputs [50].

However, the usefulness of negative prompting is not always straightforward. Studies have shown a surprising “inverse scaling law,” where larger and seemingly more capable language models can perform worse on tasks involving negated prompts [51]. This phenomenon suggests that as models become more powerful at recognising patterns from their pre-training data, they may struggle to stray from those patterns based on a simple negation word (e.g., “not”), potentially treating it as noise rather than a critical instruction [51]. This finding highlights a rather significant challenge and an active area of research. Ensuring that LLMs can robustly comprehend and adhere to both positive and negative constraints is critical for their safe and reliable deployment.

3.4.5.2 Prompt Chaining

For tasks that are too complex to be resolved by a single instruction, prompt chaining offers a powerful and modular solution [52]. This technique involves breaking down a complex task into a series of smaller, interconnected subtasks. The output from one prompt in the sequence serves as the input for the next, creating a chain of operations that guides the LLM through a structured workflow [53]. This type of approach mirrors a logical problem-solving process. Furthermore, it enhances the reliability and transparency of the model’s output.

There are various benefits of prompt chaining. By deconstructing a task, developers can achieve much more granular control over the generation process, making it easier to debug and refine specific steps within the workflow. This structured method has proven effective in a variety of applications, from

processing customer feedback pipelines to complex document analysis [53]. For instance, a complex query involving a large legal document could be chained by first prompting the model to summarise the text, then using that summary to find relevant precedents in a database, and finally generating a legal opinion based on the findings [54]. This decomposition significantly reduces the likelihood of errors that can occur when a model is overwhelmed by a single, overly complex prompt [52].

Academic research has not only validated the utility of this approach but also explored tools to make it more accessible. The "PromptChainer" project, for example, introduced an interactive interface for visually programming LLM chains, lowering the barrier for non-experts to prototype complex AI-infused applications [55].

4 Implementation

4.1 Introduction

This thesis revolves around cybersecurity knowledge, incident response cycles, and crisis response methodologies, with a particular focus on the mid-incident activities of executive-level staff. The primary objective of this thesis is to develop an open-source solution to generating cybersecurity incident response scenarios, which will be used to train executive-level staff. As the cyber regulations increase around the mandatory training of executive staff for events of cyber crisis, the necessity to create applicable cyber scenarios will grow. Although this project is purposely designed around executive staff who are mostly non-technical, its basic framework can be adapted to develop scenarios that may be used with more technical staff.

This chapter will discuss the details of the implementation of the Cyber Scenario Generator, focusing on building an adaptable, open-source platform with the aim of being user-friendly and adaptable to all sectors and corporate sizes.

4.2 Implementation of the Cyber Generator

Although there are existing solutions which utilise generative AI in the creation of accurate cybersecurity simulations, all those solutions focus on generating training for technical staff. Many of these solutions are also locked behind a paywall, often requiring a full implementation of their product into the existing environment. Additionally, many of these solutions also don't focus on non-technical staff. From research, only CISA has developed a framework that is able to be used for non-technical staff however it does not utilise generative AI, it does not focus on an incident response scenario, and the scenarios might not be applicable to every company within the sectors covered by CISA. To address these challenges, this thesis aims to develop an open-source solution that utilises LLMs for the generation of unique, and applicable scenarios.

A significant part of this solution is the choosing of an LLM which has relevant cybersecurity knowledge, can reference existing threats in appropriate sectors, and can be implemented with little to no cost. As this project is grounded in LLMs, the generation of a prompt that can guide an LLM towards the expected output is gravely important. As discussed in previous sections, LLMs work on a probability basis and may sometimes hallucinate. To prevent these challenges, building an appropriate prompt that revolves around real cyber frameworks like MITRE and can reference previous historical threats is also important. Furthermore, the generator must be user-friendly to encourage its use. Creating a complex to use solution would defeat the purpose of creating this generator, therefore it is important to account for the user experience throughout this implementation.

4.3 Choosing of the Large Language Model

There is a vast variety of LLMs currently available online at no charge. Additionally, it is possible to download pre-trained models from websites such as huggingface.co and deploy them on a local server using solutions such as LM Studio.

Local deployment of an LLM is a very viable path to go down, however, it has some limitations. Locally training an LLM for the specific task of generating cyber scenarios would require the collection of an appropriate training dataset. This would involve a pre-curated set of incident write-ups that are available online, training using the MITRE ATT&CK framework, and any appropriate academic and industry documentation on cybersecurity terminology. Additionally, existing cybersecurity scenarios would have to be curated to use for training, so as to guide the model in the generation of its output. Furthermore, one disadvantage of this approach over an LLM that is available online is the lack of up-to-date knowledge. Many online-hosted LLMs now have the ability to search through existing online databases. Although this approach would allow for a very refined model for this specific task, it may be prone to hallucination, an appropriate dataset may be difficult to define, and depending on the dataset may have large limitations in regards of certain industry contexts. Finally, the conclusive challenge is that the thesis proposes an open-source solution, therefore, a solution that requires the local deployment of a large language model may be a limiting factor for some.

Unlike locally deployed models, the full training datasets of models online can sometimes be publicly restricted. There are a select few model owners that are transparent around what data was used to in training of the LLM however, much more are secretive around the datasets with only vague details being published. This does create a challenge in choosing an LLM that is available online due to concerns around appropriate cybersecurity knowledge. Additional factors were also considered around the cost of use, cost of Application Programming Interface (API) integration, and availability of the models.

For the purposes of this thesis, two models were shortlisted and evaluated due to their cost, accessibility of API integration, and cybersecurity framework and technological knowledge. The models that were shortlisted are ChatGPT and Google Gemini. To expand on this, both models have been shown to have a large knowledge set of cybersecurity. This has been tested using a variety of prompts that questioned both cybersecurity basics and more complex problems. This has also been validated through professional research of articles by experts in the cybersecurity field. ChatGPT has what may be considered as slightly outdated knowledge as the training dataset cutoff was September 2021, however it has been updated to allow it to fetch and use real-time information from the web. Similarly, Gemini is much more up to date with its training, as its cutoff was early 2023. Furthermore, as Gemini is a model owned by Google, it is integrated with Google Search and has the ability to include it in its responses. Lastly, API integration of both models. ChatGPT does not offer a free tier for its API. Testing the integration of its API would require a paid subscription, therefore during the testing only the web interface of

ChatGPT was used. Unlike ChatGPT, Google Gemini does provide a free tier however it does not come without limitations. Gemini does not offer context caching when using the free tier, and for some models, it does not offer grounding with Google search, which may affect responses that may need to integrate more up-to-date information.

4.4 Prompt Building

The main goal of this thesis revolves around generating the same type of response from an LLM repeatedly without changing the format of the output. Therefore, a correctly built prompt is crucial to the success of this implementation. It is important to structure and build the prompt appropriately to allow for the repeated generation of cyber scenarios that follow the same type of format with very little variation between scenarios and runs.

The prompt is built using various prompting techniques, which have been discussed in section 3.4. The prompt must define the context of the output and the role that the LLM must impersonate. As the output is nested in the area of cybersecurity, the LLM must take on the role of an expert in the cybersecurity field. Setting the role context for the LLM will allow it to impersonate the appropriate tone and relevant knowledge. Furthermore, it is important to define the technical depth of the conversation for the appropriate audience. In the context of this thesis, the audience will be the executive staff, which in many cases tends to lack technical knowledge. It is imperative to define this to the LLM to prevent it from generating outputs that are highly technical.

To set this solution apart from other generators, it is important to instruct the model with the company context. Furthermore, companies may experience similar cyber risks within the same sector or relative to the same company size. However, it is crucial to include additional details associated with the specific company this scenario will relate to. Information such as company size, employee count, geographic location, and data centre location is imperative to include.

Next, the duration of the scenario must be defined. There are two unique durations that must be accounted for this scenario, the duration of the incident in the scenario and the availability of the audience to discuss the scenario. Firstly, cybersecurity incidents can vary in duration depending on several factors. A cyber incident can take anything from 1 minute up to an average of 162 hours to detect and respond to a breach [56]. Due to such a possible variation in the duration of a breach, it is vital to include this metric as part of the scenario generation. Secondly, due to the nature of the employment of executive staff, they may be limited to the amount of time that can be dedicated to training. Therefore, as an additional metric, the audience availability will be included in the prompt.

Finally, the prompt must include a decision tree system. The purpose behind including this is to allow executive staff to be provided with a set of options they may choose from. These options will be different decision paths, and they will define the impacts of choosing one of these options. The initiative behind including these decisions is that it allows to present the executives with

direct feedback of how different actions can impact different aspects of the company. These impacts will cover five specific areas: business impact, legal impact, regulatory compliance, operational resilience and reputation risk. Furthermore, adding these decision paths allows executives to be more immersed in the scenario alongside with a view on how various actions have different consequences.

4.5 User Experience

This generator is aimed at being utilised by a training administrator; however, it is not limited to just this group. The idea is that this scenario generator will be used as a tool to allow the creation of unique scenarios to be used within training and to allow training administrators to quickly create new scenarios. It is not limited to just training administrators therefore it is important that the solution is easy to use and can be implemented into existing processes. Therefore, it is key to allow the generator to be deployed or implemented into a process quickly.

Several considerations were taken during the design phase of this thesis. There are three main approaches that could be used for the implementation. The first approach involves building a prompt with editable elements and a specific suggestion of which model to use. This approach is extremely minimal and would allow the user to choose the LLM of their preference. Subjectively, from the perspective of user experience, this is the easiest implementation method however, the outputs may be inconsistent and may not align with the results of this thesis. Providing a user with, what essentially is a "copy-paste" method, would allow the users to adjust the prompt for their purposes however this may not guarantee the repeatability or consistency of the outputs. The advantage of this method is that the user can use the online-hosted version of models free of charge.

The second and third approaches involve the use of model APIs and code implementations. For the second approach, it would involve the creation of Python, which takes a single editable file as input and generates an output file. This approach would allow the users to adjust the necessary parameters without affecting the pre-built prompt. Additionally, the Python prompt may employ one or more models from which the user is provided with a choice of models to use. Each model included would be pre-screened to ensure their suitability for this purpose. One challenge of this implementation is that the user would need access to an API key of at least one of the available models. This may pose a monetary challenge as many of the available models place API access behind a paywall. Furthermore, another challenge is that it requires a certain level of technical knowledge. As this would be a code implementation, the user would need the appropriate infrastructure to host it and an understanding. This may prove challenging especially in more controlled environments such as, work environments where certain limitations may be implemented by information technology (IT) teams.

The third approach is like the second approach however, instead of it being client hosted, it may be server hosted. This approach would entail the implementation of a website-based system where a user interacts with a form

on a web interface. This proposition would reduce the technical burden of the second approach while also introducing an easy-to-use interface. Similar to the first approach, it would allow the user to adjust specific parameters and let them choose from a pre-screened selection of models. The challenge arises associated with API integration. Building a website that allows users to use various models for the generation of scenarios would require the integration of APIs of all the models. Once again, however, this would place a monetary barrier on this solution. Implementing API keys on the website would require charging customers for each generation of a report. An alternative would be implementing Bring-Your-Own-Key (BYOK). In theory, BYOK is a great approach as it would allow users to use the website with their own API key or request a free key from Google for the Gemini models. Theoretically, it would give the users a choice of a free or paid solution. In practice, however, this would require building in additional security controls to ensure that users' keys could not be intercepted by a malicious actor.

4.6 Conclusion

The final implementation of this generator provides an open-source solution for generating cybersecurity incident response scenarios tailored for the training of executive-level staff. It consists of two main components: a purpose-built prompt designed to guide an LLM and a user-friendly Python script to operationalise the prompt.

4.6.1 Purpose-Built Prompt

The effectiveness of this generator is dependent on a detailed, structured prompt that minimises randomness and ensures the consistent generation of high-quality, relevant scenarios. The prompt directs the LLM to assume the role of a cybersecurity expert, ensuring it considers the non-technical nature of the audience and builds a scenario around specific company details and reputable cybersecurity frameworks.

4.6.2 Python-based Code Implementation

The second implementation of this generator is a Python-based code implementation. The Python script below offers a user-friendly way of interacting with the Google Gemini API, leveraging the prompt from section 4.6.1. It is designed to be easily adaptable and requires minimal technical knowledge from the user. This implementation utilises a configuration file which contains company-specific variables, injects them into the prompt and sends the request to the LLM to generate the scenario.

4.6.2.1 Prerequisites

- Python 3: Ensure that Python 3 is installed on the machine.
- Google Gemini API Key: Obtain a free or paid version of the API key from Google AI Studio.
- Python Library: Install the necessary Python library using `pip install -q -U google-generativeai`

4.6.2.2 Required Files

The implementation requires two files to function:

- `scenario_generator.py`: The main Python script (for the full script, see chapter 7)
- `config.json`: This file contains the user-definable variables to inject into the prompt (See chapter 8)

4.6.2.3 How to Use

Step 1: Save the previously mentioned files into a directory on a local machine.

Step 2: Open `config.json` and replace “`YOUR_GEMINI_API_KEY`” with a valid API key.

Step 3: Modify the other values within `config.json` with the appropriate values for the training scenario to be generated.

Step 4: Proceed to run the script from your terminal:

- For Windows: `py scenario_generator.py`
- For Linux: `python scenario_generator.py`

5 Validation

5.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the early stages of LLM testing and the later-stage validation of the scenario generator. The chapter will describe the process that was used to choose the final LLM used, and it will also discuss the validation that was carried out to ensure the accuracy of the scenarios.

5.2 Initial Testing

The initial stages of testing revolved around the suitability of LLM to generate cybersecurity scenarios. The suitability of an LLM relates to its ability to create accurate cybersecurity scenarios. The suitability was evaluated on various criteria.

5.2.1 Knowledge of Cybersecurity Terminology

A foundational requirement for the scenario generator was the use of an LLM that has a deep and accurate understanding of the cybersecurity domain. Many LLMs have a basic understanding of simple definitions, but the validation process required much more in-depth knowledge of nuanced terms related to threats, vulnerabilities, tools and defensive measures. Modern LLMs that are trained on vast datasets from the internet generally demonstrate a strong grasp of cybersecurity terminology. However, cybersecurity is a rapidly evolving field therefore an LLM's knowledge can grow outdated. It was a requirement for an LLM to have the most up-to-date training datasets and the ability to access currently available online data.

5.2.2 Knowledge of Cybersecurity Frameworks

Beyond just terminology, it was a requirement for an LLM to comprehend and accurately apply established cybersecurity frameworks. The MITRE ATT&CK framework is a globally accessible knowledge database of adversary tactics and techniques based on real-world observation. This capability was crucial for generating realistic scenarios that can simulate and construct attack chains that mirror the behaviours of real-world malicious actors. The ability to reason within such frameworks demonstrated a much deeper and more applied understanding of the cyber threat landscape.

5.2.3 Accuracy of Scenarios

The factual accuracy of the generated scenarios is also extremely important. Inaccurate or misleading scenarios can lead to negative training outcomes. This can result in participants learning incorrect procedures or misinterpreting the nature of threats. The risk of "hallucination" was a significant concern. Evaluating accuracy required comparing the generated scenarios against trusted cyber threat intelligence and real-world incident reports.

5.2.4 Uniqueness of scenarios

To be used as an effective training tool, scenarios must be varied and not simply templates that are repeatedly used. One of the key advantages of using LLMs for the purpose of generating scenarios is their ability to generate novel content. By providing slightly different input parameters during generation, such as company size or industry, the LLM had to produce an array of unique scenarios. This is vital for keeping the exercises engaging and for preparing participants for the unpredictable nature of cyber incidents. The uniqueness was evaluated by comparing the narrative structure, technical details, and decision points of many generated scenarios to ensure they are sufficiently distinct from each other.

5.2.5 Relevance to different sectors

Cyber threats do not present themselves in the same way; they vary significantly across different industries. An attack targeting a financial institution will vary in tactics, techniques and objectives from one targeting a healthcare provider. Therefore, the LLM had to be capable of adopting scenarios to be relevant to the specific sector provided. The evaluation of sector relevance involved assessing whether the generated scenario incorporated industry-specific technologies, regulatory requirements and known threats pertinent to that field.

5.2.6 Quality of Generated Content

The overall quality of the generated content had to cover several factors, including clarity, coherence, and suitability for the target audience. For executive-level staff training, the content must be largely non-technical, focus on business impact and strategic decision-making. The generated narrative should be coherent and logically structured, presenting a clear chain of events and consequences. Ultimately, the goal is to produce a scenario that is informative and engaging, but also immersive for participants.

5.3 Testing with Professionals

The previous section discussed the initial testing steps that were undertaken in evaluating the suitability of an LLM for the purpose of generating scenarios. While those evaluations were able to measure an LLM's technical knowledge of cybersecurity, the actual test of a generated cybersecurity scenario lay in testing its practical application. To bridge the gap between theoretical accuracy and practical effectiveness, it was important to evaluate the scenario in real-world situations. Two distinct groups of individuals were interacted with for the testing: cybersecurity professionals and executive leaders. The use of a human-in-the-loop validation process was essential for refining the outputs from the generator and ensuring the scenarios are not only realistic but also fit for the purpose of training.

The primary objective of testing with cybersecurity professionals was to perform a technical and procedural validation. Due to their vast experience, the

professionals were able to evaluate the plausibility of the scenario from both an attacker's and defender's perspectives. Feedback was gathered through a structured review where professionals were asked to analyse the scenario by scrutinising the attack chain for logical consistency and technical practicality. They evaluated whether the described adversary tactics, techniques and procedures (TTPs) aligned with the capabilities of malicious actors and if they are relevant to the targeted industry. For example, a cybersecurity professional in the fintech industry was able to determine if the initial access vector was a credible threat to a mid-sized global financial institution. Furthermore, the professional was also able to assess if the data exfiltration and ransomware deployment timelines were realistic for the mentioned sector. Their feedback was extremely valuable in refining and adjusting the prompt to generate scenarios that are technically accurate and grounded in the reality of modern cyber threats. The feedback also allowed to prevent generating scenarios where the situations were either too simplistic or improbable.

Alongside testing with professionals for the accuracy of scenarios, testing the actual effectiveness of the scenario as a training tool was validated with a group of senior executives. Due to the nature of senior executives, the scenarios had to not be overly complicated and inundated with technical content. This specific group is mainly concerned with the business context. Therefore, the clarity of information and the relevance of decision points were crucial. The most effective way to test this was through a tabletop exercise. During the exercise, the executives were presented with a scenario relevant to their sector. The engagement levels, understanding of the scenario and the quality of discussions were observed.

Following the exercise, a debrief session was held with the senior executive audience, focusing on a set of specific questions:

- Was the language clear and free of any confusing terminology?
- Did the business impacts feel accurate and significant?
- Were the provided decision points challenging?
- Did the decision points provoke a meaningful discussion around risk, resource allocation and communication strategies?
- Did the scenario accurately simulate the pressure of a real crisis scenario?

The feedback received from the executives was used to fine-tune the prompt's instruction regarding tone, non-technical language and accuracy of the scenario. By incorporating this feedback from both groups, the generator was able to be iteratively improved to produce engaging scenarios that successfully achieved core learning objectives.

6 Conclusion

The aim of this thesis was to address a critical gap in cybersecurity training: the need for realistic, dynamically generated, and accessible training scenarios aimed at executive-level staff. The primary objective was to develop an open-source Cyber Simulation Scenario Generator based on a Large Language Model, moving beyond static and manually created tabletop exercises. This project was driven by the increasing regulatory pressure and the need for leadership that is adept at strategic decision-making during a cyber crisis. The research successfully navigated the complexities of selecting an LLM, prompt engineering, and the practical implementation.

6.1 Conclusion

The central aim of this thesis, creating a tool that utilises LLMs to develop realistic cyber scenarios for executive-level staff, has been successfully achieved. The research confirmed that modern LLMs possess the required knowledge of cybersecurity terminology and frameworks to generate technically plausible scenarios. The evaluation of various models, including ChatGPT, Gemini, and Claude, revealed that while most models have a foundation understanding of cybersecurity, models with access to up-to-date information and strong reasoning capabilities are particularly well-suited for this task.

A significant contribution of this thesis is the development of a purpose-built structured prompt. The research demonstrates that a well-engineered prompt is the foundation of generating consistent, high-quality outputs from an LLM. By employing a combination of role-based prompting, instruction-based guidance and a constrained output format, it was possible to direct an LLM to produce scenarios that are technically sound and tailored to a non-technical executive audience. The prompts design, which incorporates specific company context, variable incident timelines, and a decision-tree structure, directly addresses the limitation of existing training solutions. This ensures that the generated scenarios are not generic, one-fits-all solutions but are directly relevant to the organisation in question, increasing their value and impact.

The implementation of the generator as a Python-based tool with a user-friendly configuration file strikes a balance between customisability and ease of use. This approach allows the creation of cybersecurity scenarios, which allows training administrators to generate new, relevant scenarios quickly. By opting for an open-source model with a freely accessible API, this work removes the significant cost barrier and proprietary lock-in that many commercial solutions employ.

Furthermore, the validation process underlines the importance of human expertise in the development lifecycle of AI-driven tools. Testing generated scenarios with both cybersecurity professionals and senior executives provides a vital feedback loop. Technical experts were able to validate the plausibility of the attack chains and progression of incidents, ensuring that the scenarios were realistic. Simultaneously, executive feedback was crucial in refining the tone,

clarity and strategic relevance of the narrative. This human-in-the-loop approach was proven essential to mitigate the inherent risks of LLMs, such as hallucinations and factual inaccuracies. The process confirmed that while LLMs can be used to automate the creative and structural aspects of scenario generation, human input remains critical for final validation and alignment.

In conclusion, this thesis has successfully demonstrated the viability and value of using LLMs to generate high-quality cybersecurity simulation scenarios. It has delivered a complete, open-source solution, comprising of a purpose-built prompt and a practical Python-based implementation. The project not only meets its initial objectives but also contributes a foundational framework that can be built upon to bridge the gap between AI capabilities and the strategic needs of modern cybersecurity.

6.2 Future Work

This thesis lays a robust foundation however, the rapidly evolving nature of artificial intelligence and the cyber threat landscape presents numerous opportunities for future work. The following are areas which there are opportunities for expanding on the existing work.

First, enhancing the interactivity and dynamism of the scenarios. The current implementation generates a complete decision tree at once. A more advanced implementation could involve a real-time, interactive model where the LLM dynamically generates the next phase of the scenario based on the live decisions of the executive group. This would require more complex prompt chaining and state management, but it would result in a much more immersive experience. This would also allow to simulate the fluidity of a real crisis.

Second, the user experience of the generator could be improved by implementing a graphical user interface (GUI). While the current Python script and configuration file are functional, a web-based or desktop application would elevate the user experience, making it more accessible to a broader audience. Implementing a GUI could guide the user through inputting the company context, selecting different threat types, and could offer pre-built templates, further lowering the entry barrier.

Third, integrating a more formal feedback mechanism and performance metrics into the training process. Future versions of the tool could include a post-simulation module that prompts the executives to reflect on their decisions and would map their choices to best-practice incident response frameworks. An LLM could be utilised to analyse the decisions made throughout the exercise to provide automated feedback, highlighting the areas of strength and opportunities for improvement in the crisis management approach.

Lastly, expanding the scope of the scenarios beyond just the initial incident response phase would be a valuable addition. Future work could develop scenarios that cover the full crisis lifecycle, including post-incident recovery, regulatory reporting and long-term remediation. This would provide a much more holistic training experience, preparing executives for the challenges that follow a significant cyber attack. This could also involve incorporating other relevant frameworks beyond MITRE ATT&CK, such as the NIST Cybersecurity Framework and the ISO/IEC 27001 framework, to broaden the training scope.

7 Code

```
# Importing of required libraries
import google.generativeai as genai
from datetime import datetime
import json
import os

# Purpose of this function is to import the config.json
file into the script
def import_config(config_path='config.json'):
    try:
        with open(config_path, 'r') as f:
            return json.load(f)
    except FileNotFoundError:
        print(f"Error: Configuration file '{config_path}'
not found.")
        return None
    except json.JSONDecodeError:
        print(f"Error: Could not decode JSON from
'{config_path}'.")
        return None

# Purpose of this function is to write the output to a
markdown file
def save_scenario_to_file(scenario_text,
industry_sector):
    # Create a unique filename using industry sector and
current timestamp
    timestamp = datetime.now().strftime("%Y%m%d_%H%M%S")
    filename =
f"Scenario_{industry_sector}_{timestamp}.md"

    try:
        with open(filename, 'w', encoding='utf-8') as f:
            f.write(scenario_text)
            print(f"\nScenario successfully saved to file:
{filename}")
    except IOError as e:
        print(f"\nError: Could not save scenario to file.
{e}")

# Purpose of this function is to build the prompt using a
pre-written prompt and imported variables
# and to return the build prompt
def build_prompt(config):

    prompt_template = f"""
You are a world-class cybersecurity expert and crisis
management consultant. Your task is to generate a
detailed, realistic, and sector-specific cybersecurity
```

incident response scenario for the executive leadership team of a given company. The entire scenario and all its components must be presented in a clear, concise, and non-technical language suitable for a non-technical audience of company executives. Each incident throughout the incident response scenario must contribute to further escalation of the incident.

The scenario must be structured as a decision-tree exercise that unfolds over a specified duration.

****Company Context:****

* ****Industry/Sector:**** {config['industry_sector']}
* ****Company Size:**** {config['company_size']}
* ****Employee Count:**** {config['employee_count']}
* ****Geographic Location(s):****
{config['geographic_locations']}

****Scenario Parameters:****

* ****Incident Type:**** {config['incident_type']}
* ****Total Scenario Duration (Real-time):****
{config['exercise_duration']}
* ****Incident Timeline (In-scenario):****
{config['incident_timeline']}
* ****Amount of unique incidents:****
{config['incident_amount']}

****Output Structure:****

****1. Executive Situation Briefing (Initial Inject):****

* ****What We Know:**** A summary of the incident as it is first presented to the executive team.

* ****Initial Business Impact:**** The immediate, tangible effects on the business.

* ****Key Stakeholders Involved:**** List the internal and external parties immediately involved or impacted.

****2. Decision Point 1:****

* ****Option A:**** [Describe the first possible course of action that is based on Business Impact].

* ****Option B:**** [Describe a second possible course of action that is based on Legal impact].

* ****Option C:**** [Describe a third possible course of action that is based on Regulatory Compliance].

* ****Option D:**** [Describe a second possible course of action that is based on Operational Resilience].

* ****Option E:**** [Describe a third possible course of action that is based on Reputation Risk].

****3. Consequences and Escalation (Based on Decision):****

* For **each** of the options (A, B, C, D, and E) from Decision Point 1, provide a detailed "If you chose this option..." outcome.

* This outcome must describe the evolving situation and its impact across the specific domains that were provided.

4. Further Decision points:

* Based on the provided amount of unique incidents, generate that amount of further escalating incidents. Ensure that the incident escalation follows the known vectors as described in the MITRE ATT&CK framework.

* Provide five new, distinct options for the executive team to consider.

5. Scenario Conclusion:

* Provide a concluding summary that outlines the potential final state of the company based on a plausible path through the decision points.

* Include key learning objectives and discussion points for the executive team.

Begin the generation now based on the provided context and parameters.

```
"""
```

```
    return prompt_template
```

```
#
```

```
def generate_scenario(api_key, prompt):
```

```
    """Sends the prompt to the Gemini API and returns the generated text."""
```

```
    try:
```

```
        genai.configure(api_key=api_key)
```

```
        model = genai.GenerativeModel('gemini-2.5-flash')
```

```
        response = model.generate_content(prompt)
```

```
        return response.text
```

```
    except Exception as e:
```

```
        return f"An error occurred during API interaction: {e}"
```

```
def main():
```

```
    print("*** Cyber Scenario Generator ***")
```

```
    # Load configuration
```

```
    config = import_config()
```

```
    if not config:
```

```
        return
```

```
    # Get API key
```

```
    api_key = os.getenv("GEMINI_API_KEY",
config.get("api_key"))
    if not api_key or api_key == "YOUR_GEMINI_API_KEY":
        print("Error: API key not found. Please set it in
config.json or as an environment variable
'GEMINI_API_KEY'.")
        return

    # Build the prompt
    print("Building the prompt with using the provided
configuration...")
    final_prompt = build_prompt(config)

    # Generate the scenario
    print("Generating scenario...")
    scenario_text = generate_scenario(api_key,
final_prompt)

    # Output the result
    print("\n*** Generated Cybersecurity Scenario ***")
    print(scenario_text)
    print("*** End of Scenario ***")

    # Save the result to a file if generation was
successful
    if "An error occurred" not in scenario_text:
        save_scenario_to_file(scenario_text,
config['industry_sector'])

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

8 Configuration File

```
{  
  "api_key": "YOUR_GEMINI_API_KEY",  
  "industry_sector": "Financial Technology (FinTech)",  
  "company_size": "Medium-sized enterprise",  
  "employee_count": "450",  
  "geographic_locations": "Headquartered in London, UK, with a data centre in  
Frankfurt, Germany",  
  "incident_type": "Ransomware Attack",  
  "exercise_duration": "90 minutes",  
  "incident_timeline": "The incident has been ongoing for 48 hours before  
executive notification",  
  "incident_amount": "5 incidents"  
}
```

9 Prompt

You are a world-class cybersecurity expert and crisis management consultant. Your task is to generate a detailed, realistic, and sector-specific cybersecurity incident response scenario for the executive leadership team of a given company. The entire scenario and all its components must be presented in a clear, concise, and non-technical language suitable for a non-technical audience of company executives. Each incident throughout the incident response scenario must contribute to further escalation of the incident.

The scenario must be structured as a decision-tree exercise that unfolds over a specified duration.

****Company Context:****

- * ****Industry/Sector:**** [Specify Sector, e.g., "Financial Technology (FinTech)"]
- * ****Company Size:**** [Specify Size, e.g., "Medium-sized enterprise"]
- * ****Employee Count:**** [Specify Employee Count, e.g., "Approximately 450 employees"]
- * ****Geographic Location(s):**** [Specify Locations, e.g., "Headquartered in London, UK, with a data centre in Frankfurt, Germany"]

****Scenario Parameters:****

- * ****Incident Type:**** [Specify Threat Type, e.g., "Ransomware Attack"]
- * ****Total Scenario Duration (Real-time):**** [Specify duration of the tabletop exercise, e.g., "90 minutes"]
- * ****Incident Timeline (In-scenario):**** [Specify duration of the fictional incident, e.g., "The incident has been ongoing for 48 hours before executive notification"]
- * ****Amount of unique incidents:**** [Specify the amount of unique incidents that happen during the incident timeline, e.g., "5 incident"]

****Output Structure:****

****1. Executive Situation Briefing (Initial Inject):****

- * ****What We Know:**** A summary of the incident as it is first presented to the executive team.
- * ****Initial Business Impact:**** The immediate, tangible effects on the business (e.g., "core customer-facing application is offline," "internal file shares are inaccessible").

* **Key Stakeholders Involved:** List the internal and external parties immediately involved or impacted (e.g., "IT Department, Legal Counsel, Customers").

2. Decision Point 1:

* **The Dilemma:** Present the first critical decision the executive team must make.

* **Option A:** [Describe the first possible course of action that is based on Business Impact].

* **Option B:** [Describe a second possible course of action that is based on Legal impact].

* **Option C:** [Describe a third possible course of action that is based on Regulatory Compliance].

* **Option D:** [Describe a second possible course of action that is based on Operational Resilience].

* **Option E:** [Describe a third possible course of action that is based on Reputation Risk].

3. Consequences and Escalation (Based on Decision):

* For **each** of the options (A, B, C, D, and E) from Decision Point 1, provide a detailed "If you chose this option..." outcome.

* This outcome must describe the evolving situation and its impact across the specific domains that were provided.

4. Further Decision points:

* Based on the provided amount of unique incidents, generate that amount of further escalating incidents. Ensure that the incident escalation follows the known vectors as described in the MITRE ATT&CK framework.

* Provide five new, distinct options for the executive team to consider.

5. Scenario Conclusion:

* Provide a concluding summary that outlines the potential final state of the company based on a plausible path through the decision points.

* Include key learning objectives and discussion points for the executive team.

Begin the generation now based on the provided context and parameters.

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